

Article

Teachers 'literacy in Information and Communication Technology in Teaching Early Childhood Education

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Abstract:

Literacy with ICT involves critical and creative thinking, digital citizenship, and the ability to use technology to meet our needs in a safe, healthy, responsible, and ethical manner. Many pupils today are proficient with some technologies and may even be more educated about its use than their teachers. this work bridges the gap in the current literature that explains the teacher ICT literacy in teaching and learning process. Finding showed that early childhood education underlined the necessity for teachers to continue integrating ICT into the classroom in order to enhance literacy. To preserve or improve the abilities to establish a data base, use a spread sheet to plot a graph, create a blog/website, and generate or amend a questionnaire online, which were determined to be inadequate or nonexistent. Hence, relevant ICT training and seminars can be provided to maintain or improve their computer literacy.

Keywords: Teacher's literacy, ICT literacy, Early Childhood Education, Technology integration

1. Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is becoming increasingly important in today's world, and its importance can be seen in many aspects of our lives (Graham & Dutlon, 2021). According to Bakuri & Amoabeng (2023) ICT enables people to communicate and collaborate with one another in real-time, regardless of their geographical location. This has revolutionized communication, making it easier and more efficient to stay in touch with friends, family, colleagues and with the internet, ICT has made it possible for people to access information on virtually any topic at any time (Szymkowiak et al., 2021). Moreover, ICT has transformed the way we learn and research, and has given people access to information that was previously unavailable to them and made it possible to automate many

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processes and tasks, reducing the need for manual labor and increasing efficiency (Wang et al., 2020). This has led to significant improvements in productivity and cost savings. ICT has made it possible to access a wide range of entertainment options, such as streaming movies and TV shows, playing video games, and listening to music (Mendoza, 2022). This has transformed the way we relax and unwind. CT has revolutionized education, making it easier and more accessible to learn. With the availability of online courses and e-learning platforms, people can now learn from anywhere in the world and at any time (Lemke & Schifferstein, 2021). Moreover, ICT has transformed the way businesses operate, making it easier to manage operations, communicate with customers, and access global markets (Stonehouse & Konina, 2020). This has opened up new opportunities for businesses and entrepreneurs and transformed the healthcare industry, making it possible to provide remote care and monitor patients' health from a distance (Ryan et al., 2023). This has led to significant improvements in patient outcomes and has reduced the need for hospital visits and transformed the way we live, work, and communicate. Its importance will only continue to grow as technology continues to advance and new innovations are developed (Fukuda, 2020).

Zhang et al. (2022) emphasized that Information and Communication Technology is increasingly becoming an integral part of education, and its importance in schools cannot be overstated. It provides teachers with new and innovative ways of teaching, making it possible to create interactive and engaging lessons that cater to different learning styles (Bhati & Song, 2019). Students can also use ICT to access a wide range of resources and educational materials online, making it easier for them to learn and understand complex topics (Das, 2019). ICT can help to improve student outcomes by providing students with access to personalized and differentiated learning experiences. This helps to ensure that students are engaged and motivated, leading to better academic performance (Alamri et al., 2021). Moreover, according to ICT helps students to develop essential digital skills and competencies, such as digital literacy, critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration (Tinmaz et al., 2023). Smyrnaiou et al. (2020) also suggested that ICT provides students and teachers with tools and resources to express themselves creatively and innovate in different subject areas. In addition, ICT is essential in schools as it enhances teaching and learning, improves student outcomes, develops digital skills, promotes creativity and innovation, streamlines administrative tasks, enhances access to information, and prepares students for the future. It is therefore important for schools to invest in ICT infrastructure and ensure that teachers are equipped with the necessary skills to effectively integrate ICT into their teaching practices (Aldosemani, 2023).

Naido (2020) argued that teachers' literacy in ICT (Information and Communication Technology) has become increasingly important in

today's digital world. With the growth of technology and the internet, it is crucial for teachers to be able to effectively integrate ICT into their teaching practices to support student learning and prepare them for the future (Starky, 2020). Das (2019) also noted that one of the primary benefits of teachers' literacy in ICT is the improvement of teaching and learning. Teachers who are literate in ICT can use technology to create interactive and engaging lessons that cater to different learning styles, and can use educational software, multimedia presentations, online resources, and virtual learning environments to help students better understand complex topics (Mohd et al., 2021). In addition, teachers who are literate in ICT are better able to adapt to the changing technological landscape (Lhendup, 2020). They can stay up-to-date with new developments and incorporate emerging technologies into their teaching practices, thus providing students with an education that is relevant to the current digital age (Saykili, 2019). Another benefit of teachers' literacy in ICT is the ability to enhance administrative tasks and with ICT literacy, teachers can efficiently manage administrative tasks such as attendance tracking, grading, report generation, and communication with parents (Hassan & Mirza, 2021). This enables them to spend more time on teaching and supporting student learning. Furthermore, teachers' ICT literacy can promote digital citizenship among students (Milenkova & Lendzhova, 2021). Teachers can teach students about the responsible use of technology, including digital safety, online etiquette, and cyberbullying (Redmond et al., 2020). Finally, teachers' ICT literacy is essential for preparing students for the future. For instance, as technology continues to transform the workforce, it is important that students are equipped with the necessary digital skills and competencies to succeed in the 21st century (Khan et al., 2022). In addition, teachers' literacy in ICT is essential for improving teaching and learning, enhancing administrative tasks, promoting digital citizenship, and preparing students for the future. It is important that teachers continue to develop their ICT literacy skills so that they can provide students with a high-quality education that is relevant to the current digital age (Garzon et al., 2020).

It is essential for teachers to be literate in ICT in today's world. According to Hasin & Nasir (2021) failure to do so can lead to inadequate teaching and learning experiences, limited access to digital resources, difficulty in teaching essential digital skills, ineffective communication, and difficulty in adapting to new technology. It is important for schools to provide teachers with adequate training and support to ensure that they are equipped with the necessary skills to effectively use technology in their teaching practices (Winter et al., 2021). Teachers who are not literate in ICT may not be able to effectively use technology in their teaching practices (Kanchai, 2021). This can result in inadequate teaching and learning experiences for students,

which can affect their academic performance and overall success (Lemay et al., 2021). Anyim (2021) stated that teachers who are not literate in ICT may not be able to access and use digital resources such as e-books, online educational materials, and multimedia resources in their teaching. Teachers who are not literate in ICT may not be able to teach essential digital skills to their students (Falloon, 2020). Teachers who are not literate in ICT may struggle to communicate effectively with students and other teachers (Lin et al., 2022). Moreover, technology is constantly evolving, and teachers who are not literate in ICT may struggle to adapt to new technologies and teaching practices (Anani et al., 2021). This can limit their ability to effectively use technology in the classroom and stay up-to-date with new teaching methods (Sofi-Karim et al., 2023).

Assessing teacher ICT literacy is essential to ensure that teachers have the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively use technology in their teaching practices. It helps to identify training needs, improve student outcomes, ensure effective use of technology, encourage innovation, and keep up-to-date with new technologies. Schools should prioritize the assessment of teacher ICT literacy and provide adequate training and support to ensure that teachers are equipped with the necessary skills to provide high-quality teaching and learning experiences for their students. Moreover, assessing teacher ICT (Information and Communication Technology) literacy is essential to ensure that teachers have the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices.

Presently, in the Philippines, there have been limited evaluations on teachers' literacy in ICT, in the context of Early Childhood Education. Thus, this work bridges the gap in the current literature that explains the teacher ICT literacy in teaching and learning process. The environment of the study was Talisay city central elementary and Mohon Elementary School. This study employed a descriptive method research design utilizing quantitative approaches. Vaismoradi et al. (2013) noted that descriptive research is a research method describing the characteristics of the population or phenomenon studied. Deeks et al. (2019) emphasized that descriptive statistics utilizes data collection and analysis techniques that yield reports and summarize the important data.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Literacy Skills of the Respondents in the Use of ICT in Teaching ECE Learners

S/ N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Produce a text using a word processing programme	3.35	Highly Skilled
2	Use emails to communicate with others	3.42	Highly Skilled
3	Capture and edit digital photos, movies or other images	2.95	Skilled
4	Edit text online containing internet links and images	2.98	Skilled
5	Create a database	2.30	Less Skilled
6	Create and/or edit a questionnaire online	2.32	Less Skilled
7	Email a file to someone	3.12	Skilled
8	Organize computer files in folders and subfolders	3.08	Skilled
9	Use a spread sheet (e.g., Excel)	3.23	Skilled
10	Use a spread sheet to plot a graph	2.50	Skilled
11	Create a presentation with simple animation functions	2.55	Skilled
12	Create a presentation with video or audio clips	2.67	Skilled
13	Participate in a discussion forum on the internet	2.68	Skilled
14	Create and maintain blogs or web sites	1.57	Not Skilled
15	Participate in social networks	2.87	Skilled
16	Download and install software on a computer	2.65	Skilled
17	Download or upload curriculum resources from/to websites or learning platforms for students to use	3.10	Skilled
18	Teach students how to behave safely online	3.15	Skilled
19	Teach students how to behave ethically online	2.97	Skilled
20	Prepare materials to use with an interactive whiteboard	2.02	Less Skilled
21	Use a Student Response System (e.g., ActiVote, ActivExpression or other)	1.65	Not Skilled
22	Programming	1.48	Not Skilled
Aggregate Weighted Mean		2.66	Skilled

Table 1 shows the summary that the level of literacy skills of the respondents in the use of ICT is found to be “Skilled” with 2.66 aggregated weighted mean. This implies that teachers already integrated ICT in teaching ECE even though there are challenges that they encountered due lack of training to have the specific skills needed in ICT. The Teachers' Use of ICT in Implementing the Competency-Based Curriculum study by Murithi and Yoo (2021) revealed that despite teachers' perceptions that using computers was essential; they had trouble incorporating technology into their courses. Teachers believed those schools' ICT resources were insufficient, which made it difficult to incorporate technology into the rollout of the new curriculum.

Table 2. ICT Integration knowledge in teaching ECE

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I feel confident learning new computer skills.	3.55	Very High
2	I find it easier to teach by using ICT	3.53	Very High
3	I am aware of the great opportunities that ICT offers for effective teaching	3.62	Very High
4	I think that ICT supported teaching makes learning more effective.	3.63	Very High
5	The use of ICT helps teachers to improve teaching with more updated materials.	3.75	Very High
6	I think the use of ICT improves the quality of teaching.	3.75	Very High
7	I think the use of ICT helps to prepare teaching resources and materials	3.78	Very High
8	The use of ICT enables the students' to be more active and engaging in the lesson	3.77	Very High
9	I have more time to cater to students' need if ICT is used in teaching	3.18	High
10	I can still have an effective teaching without the use of ICT.	3.12	High
11	I think the use of ICT in teaching is a waste of time	1.85	Low
12	I am confident that my students learn best without the help of ICT.	1.87	Low
13	The classroom management is out of control if ICT is used in teaching	1.77	Low
14	Students' pay less attention when ICT is used in teaching	1.78	Low
15	Students' makes no effort for their lesson if ICT is used in teaching	1.80	Low
Aggregate Weighted Mean		2.98	High

Table 2 revealed that the summary of the extent of the perceived ICT integration knowledge of the respondents in teaching ECE is "High" with aggregate weighted mean of 3.01. This may imply that teachers in majority already equipped in different strategies and application of effective instructional materials based in ICT integration knowledge most of the teachers have. Teachers also show confirmation of the importance of ICT in integration of learning but some of the consideration seen in the data reflected in table considered as "low" In his study, Shah (2021) explained that teachers' perceptions of ICT integration at the 80 private primary level show that teachers in public schools perceived ICT integration as low because there are fewer chances of having full equipment to use, whereas teachers in private schools demonstrated a positive extent of perceived ICT knowledge

because they were able to use up-to-date technology so they could integrate ICT into teaching ECE.

Table 3. Level of Effectiveness of ICT Integration for ECE Learning

S/ N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	ICT allows students' to be more creative and imaginative	3.48	Very Effective
2	The use of ICT helps students to find related knowledge and information for learning	3.62	Very Effective
3	The use of ICT encourages students to communicate more with their classmates	3.27	Very Effective
4	The use of ICT increases students' confidence to participate actively in the class	3.20	Effective
5	I think students learn more effectively with the use of ICT.	3.28	Very Effective
6	I think the use of ICT helps to broaden students' knowledge paradigm.	3.38	Very Effective
7	I think the use of ICT helps to improve students' ability specifically in reading, writing.	3.28	Very Effective
8	The students are more behaved and under control with the use of ICT.	2.83	Effective
9	The use of ICT enables students to express their ideas and thoughts better.	3.22	Effective
10	The use of ICT promotes active and engaging lesson for students' best learning experience	3.47	Very Effective
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.30	Very Effective

Table 3 shows that the level of effectiveness of ICT integration for ECE learning is "Very Effective" with 3.30 aggregate weighted mean. Data implies positive impact to learners in ECE. Similar studies of Akram et. al (2022), findings suggest that teachers have a positive level of perception of ICT integration in learning. Through ICT, the respondents have more extensive skills, and it is more helpful to have a positive interaction between the student and the teacher.

Table 4. Test of Significant Relationship between the Teachers' Literacy Skills in ICT and the Extent of Integration in Teaching Early Childhood Education

Variables	r-value	Strength of Correlation	P-value	Decision	Result
Literacy Skills in ICT	0.182	Negligible Positive	0.165	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 4 showed that there is no significant relationship with 0.165, which is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$), which indicates that the null hypothesis is accepted. This data implies that teachers' literacy skills do impact the extent of their integration in teaching ECE. As a consequence, it is clear that the demographic profile of the respondents shown in the tables has no bearing on whether literacy skills in ICT are present in the curriculum or the extent of integration. This indicates that the teachers' respondents each have a unique approach to incorporating ICT into their present teaching.

Discussions

The purpose of the research was to evaluate the level of preparedness of ECE teachers to make use of ICT in early childhood education. Sixty teachers from Talisay City Central Elementary School and Mohon Elementary School responded to the survey questionnaires, which is the total number of students and teachers that were included in the sample. Primary level classes are taught by the vast majority of female educators who hold master's degrees and put in an average of 20–29 hours of work each week toward reading and numeracy instruction. The average age of one of them is between 26 and 35 years old. The vast majority of educators have an overall teaching experience of less than five years and make extensive use of smart phones as an integrating tool. In addition, it was discovered via the analysis of the data that the educators have a "high" level of perceived ICT integration knowledge in teaching and have a "skilled" level of ICT literacy when it comes to implementing ICT in the classroom setting for early childhood education. On the other side, the level of efficacy of information and communication technology integration for early childhood education is "extremely effective." In addition, the data presented demonstrated that the level of literacy abilities that instructors had in regards to ICT is "not significant" to the degree of integration.

Conclusion

The study's findings show that ECE teachers still need to improve and develop a number of abilities, particularly when working with learners in primary-level classrooms, despite the fact that they believe they are skilled and effective at integrating ICT into their instruction. As a result of this study, it was determined that the literacy of ICT teachers is not related to the degree of their use of it in the classroom because even though they may be literate in its manipulation and application, they may choose not to utilize it because of potential integration challenges. Early childhood education highlighted the need to continue the practice of teachers in integrating ICT in teaching to increase literacy. To maintain or enhance the skills to create data base, use spread sheet to

plot the graph and create a blog /website and create or edit questionnaire online found too less skilled or no skilled at all. Thus, appropriate ICT training and seminars may be given to them to sustain or improve their literacy skills in ICT.

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